

Spectrophotometric Studies on Iron(III) and Copper(II) Complexes

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Manuscript received 3 July 1973; revised 10 September 1973; accepted 9 November 1973

The 1 : 1 green coloured complexes formed by iron(III) and copper(II) with 2-hydroxy-5-methylbutyrophene semicarbazone (HMBS) have been studied spectrophotometrically. The colourless complexes of iron(III) formed by ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid, oxalic acid, citric acid and malonic acid have also been studied spectrophotometrically using (HMBS) as an auxiliary ligand. Results show that iron(III) forms 1 : 1 complexes with these carboxylic acids at low pH.

THE chelating tendencies of 2-hydroxyphenone semicarbazone have not been investigated fully. The present paper describes the results on composition and stability of the chelates of iron(III) and copper(II) with HMBS. It also describes the use of HMBS as an auxiliary ligand in determining the composition of the colourless complexes of iron(III) formed by ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid, oxalic acid, malonic acid and citric acid with iron(III) in acid media.

Experimental

HMBS (M.P. 188°) was prepared by the procedure as shown earlier¹. Standard reagent solutions were prepared by dissolving weighed amounts of reagent in pure methanol. All other chemicals used were at A.R. quality. The stock iron(III) and copper(II) solutions were prepared as shown earlier^{2,3}. The

stock solutions of the carboxylic acids were prepared by dissolving a calculated amount of each in 0.01M HNO₃. Dilute solutions were obtained as and when needed by diluting the stock solutions with 0.01M HNO₃. All aqueous solutions were prepared in water twice distilled over alkaline permanganate.

Absorbance measurements were made on Zeiss-specol using 1 cm matched cells. All measurements were carried out at 30° ± 1° in a 50% methanol, 50% water (by volume) medium adjusted to 0.005M with respect to nitric acid.

Results and Discussion

The nature of complexes formed in iron(III)-HMBS and copper(II)-HMBS systems were determined by the method of Vosburgh and Cooper⁴. The observations showed that in both the cases only one complex was formed. The λ_{max} of the two

Fig. 1. Job's curves for FeHMBS²⁺-EDTA system.
Curve A : FeHMBS²⁺-0.01M HNO₃
Curve B : FeHMBS²⁺-EDTA
Curve C : Difference of curve A and B.

complexes are given in Table 1. The compositions of the complexes were determined by three methods, Job's method⁵, slope-ratio method⁶ and mole-ratio method⁷. The results of all the three methods showed that the stoichiometric ratio of the metal and HMBS is 1 : 1 in both the cases. The apparent stability constants of the complexes were calculated from absorbance data by the method of Mukherji and Dey⁸. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

System	λ_{max} (nm)	log K
Fe(III)-HMBS	620	3.7
Cu(II)-HMBS	690	3.5

Colourless complexes of iron(III) :

The method used here has been described earlier by Babko *et al.*⁹. The equilibrium studied may be described as :

where, B^{-m} = carboxylate anion.

To determine the composition of iron(III)-carboxylate complexes, these equilibria were studied by the following method.

In this method a solution containing FeHMBS^{+2} ($5 \times 10^{-4}M$) was prepared by mixing equal volumes of equimolar ($1 \times 10^{-3}M$) solutions of iron(III) and

HMBS. The continuous variation⁵ studies were then carried out using equimolar solutions ($5 \times 10^{-4}M$) of FeHMBS^{+2} and carboxylic acid. The absorbances were measured at the λ_{max} (620 nm) of FeHMBS^{+2} . Two sets of solutions for each equilibrium, one with and the other without carboxylic acid were prepared. The difference in the absorbance of the pair of corresponding solutions for the two sets corresponds to the Y function of the Job's curve. The typical results are shown in Fig. 1 for FeHMBS^{+2} -EDTA system. It can be seen from the figure that the maximum decolourization was observed at a ratio of iron(III) : EDTA = 1 : 1. This indicates the formation of a complex corresponding to the formula FeEDTA^- under the experimental conditions used. Similar results were obtained in other systems involving oxalic acid, malonic acid and citric acid.

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